

PARIHAR TEMPLES FOR RAHU AND KETHU

S. Maharaj* & Dr. A. Kalaivani**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Nine planets govern us. According to our previous janma karma we enjoy everything. If we had done good karma in previous janma, we live happily in current janma. If we had done sin in previous janma, we live with lot of suffers and worries in current karma. To reduce our negative karma, temples are the most helpful one. The vibration of the temple reduces the negative karma and ready to give positive vibes. Rahu and Kethu are shadow planets. So, they are very important.

Key Words: Rahu, Kethu, Sarpa Dosa, Kal Sarpa Dosa, Nivarana, Temple, Details

Introduction:

Human beings always surrender God. They worship God to remove obstacles in their life. For doing marriage, getting job, carrying a baby, to build a house, to buy a vehicle they go to temple and do vituals. In Tamilnadu there are somany temples for nine planets. People do there special poojas to cool down the God. Rahu and kethu are shadow planets. Doing parihar for this planets change our lives.

What is Sarpa dosa?

In one's horoscope Rahu or kethu Stands in Lagna or Second bhava it is called sarpa dosa. It is the dangerous one. This position gives delayed marriage, intercaste marriage, health issues, illegal contacts and divorce So, graga shanthi (Nivarana Parihar Pooja) is very very important. Some temples are very famous for doing the above pooja. We will understand the details of the temples in this article.

What is Kal Sarpa Dosa?

When all planets between Rahu and Kethu or when all the stars of fortune or planets get trapped in a vicious circle or when all the stars of fortune concentrate at one position in a horoscope. Then it is termed as conjunction of planets and then it's time for you to understand that you have kalsarpa dosa in your life. Rahu means mouth of the snake. Kethu means rest of the body of the snake. Rahu and Kethu in the form of a poisonous snake swallow all other planets in the kundali and thus make them inactive and keeps a person away from their blessings and positive energy. And since then the problems in one's life begin. It brings disrespect to a person in the society. Bring hurdles in all the progress of life. Delays ones marriage and child birth etc...

Some Parihar temples for Rahu, Kethu:

- Peraiyur Naganatha Swamy Temple, near Poonamaravathi, Pudukottai district.
- Kavunthambadi, Tambikalai Ayyan Temple, Thanga medu, Erode district.
- Kuruvi thurai Temple, Chozhvanthan, near Madurai
- Naganatha Swamy Temple, Nayinar kovil near Paramakudi.
- Mannar Salai Temple, Alapuzha in Kerala
- Sankaran kovil Temple, near Kovilpatty
- Thiruneermalai Thooma kethu Temple, near Pallavaram,
- Thirupamburam, near Mayiladuthurai.
- Snake Vinayaga Temple, Pavanasam, near Thanjavur
- Thirumurugan poondi Temple
- Kathiramangalam Vanadurga
- Kalahastheeswarar Temple Uthampalayam
- Patteeswaram Durga devi near kumbakonam.
- Mathana gopalaswamy Temple, Madurai.
- Thiru Kandiyur Bramma Temple, near Thiruvaiyaru.
- Maechery Patrakali – Salem
- Thethupathy Rajakaliamman, Dindigul
- Nachiyar kovil kal karudan
- Kodaga Nallur Temple, near Tirunelveli
- Trichy Pichandavar Temple, Five face Ganapathi
- Thiruvanaikaval, near Trichy
- Samayapuram Mariamman, near Trichy
- Bhuvaneswari temple, Pudukottai

- Nagaraja temple, Kodumudi, near karur
- Karpaga vinayagar, Pillaiyarpatty
- Naga theertham, chozha vanthan, near Madurai
- Keezh Perumpallam near seergazhi.
- Thiruthali Nathar, Thirupathur
- Arthanareeswarar, Thiruchengode
- Nagaraja Temple, Nagercoil
- Thiruvashi Natarajar, near Trichy
- Patanjali temple in Rameswaram
- Kalahasthi Temple, Andra Pradesh
- Kanipakkam Vinayaga in Andra Pradesh
- Ramanuja Temple, Sriperumpudhur
- Chitragupta Temple in Kanchipuram

Temples for Rahu Parihar:

Rahu in 6/8/12 house in one's horoscope or debilitation or in enemy house One should do preethi for Rahu. The following temples are best for doing Rahu preethi.

- Tirunageswaram (Near Kumbakonam)
- Irukkankudi (Near Sattur)
- Samayapuram (Near Trichy)
- Sankarankovil (Near Rajapalayam)

Tirunageswaram Temple History:

In this temple the abishega milk colour is changed from white to blue. Doing this ritual removes the Rahu dosa.

Route:

- Kilometer from Uppiliappan temple

Poweful Tips:

- Rahu kala milk abishegam gives quick results.

Temples for Kethu Parihar:

Kethu in 6/8/12 house in one's horoscope or debilitation or in enemy house One should do preethi for Kethu. The following temples are best for doing Kethu preethi.

- Keezh Perumpallam (Near Seergazhi)
- Naganatha swami (Peraiyur)
- Karpaga Vinayagar Pillayar Patty
- Chitra gupta temple kanchipuram.

Keezh Perum Pallam Temple History:

Devas and asuras churned the milky ocean for nectar using Mount Meru as the rod and Vasuki the snake as the rope . After receiving nectar they throw Vasuki. Vasuki fell down at bamboo tope. It prayed shiva and got the place of planet and stayed in keezh perumpallam.

Route:

- 22 Kilometers from seergazhi.

Powerful Tips:

Doing pooja for kethu in Yamakanda timing is very best to get quick result.

Best Star for Parihar:

Ayilyam star which is in cancer sign is the best star for doing sarpa dosa parihar and kalsarpa dosa parihar. Because Athishesan was athi devatha for Ayilya. Caduceus symbol is the symbol for Ayilyam star.

Best Time for Kethu Parihar:

Yamakandam is the best time for Kethu Parihar.

Day	Yamakandam Timing
Sunday	Noon to 1.30 pm.
Monday	10.30 am to Noon
Tuesday	9 am to 10.30 am
Wednesday	7.30 am to 9 am
Thursday	6 am to 7.30 am
Friday	3 pm to 4.20 pm
Saturday	1.30 pm to 3 pm

In the above chart Saturday timing is not favour for us. Because that time all temples should be closed.

Best Time for Rahu Parihar:

Rahu kalam is the best time for Rahu parihar

Day	Rahu kalam Timing
Sunday	4.30 pm to 6 pm
Monday	7.30 am to 9 am
Tuesday	3 pm to 4.30 pm
Wednesday	Noon to 1.30 pm
Thursday	1.30 pm to 3 pm
Friday	10.30 am to Noon
Saturday	9 am to 10.30 am

In this above chart Thursday timing is not favour for us. Because that time all temples should be closed.

Conclusion:

One should worship Rahu and Kethu according to his / her dash, bukthi and kochar transit. It will solve one's problem and save him / her as a shield. So, select your temple and worship to receive the divine energy which protects us.

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